

2-Phenyl-4-thiazolybenzoyl Ketoximes

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Substituted benzoylacetones, converted into α - γ -dioxo β -oximino- α -phenylbutanes, have been brominated in ether and the bromo compounds, thus obtained, condensed with substituted thiobenzamides to yield 2-phenyl-4-thiazolybenzoyl ketoximes.

Various methods of preparing phenylthiazolyl diketones are under investigation in this laboratory. As a preliminary step in the preparation of the above, 2-phenyl-4-thiazolybenzoyl ketoximes have been prepared by the condensation of α - γ -dioxo β -oximino- α -phenyl- δ -bromobutanes with substituted thiobenzamides, as shown below:

(where R = H or Cl; R₁=R₂=H, Me, Cl, OMe).

Further work on the hydrolysis of the above ketoximes to diketones is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiobenzamides.—To substituted benzonitriles (20 g.), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (100 ml), triethanolamine (2 ml) was added. Dry H₂S gas was then passed through this solution till saturation (24 hr.). The flask was corked tightly and left undisturbed for 2 days. The contents were then diluted with water and the solid separating was crystallised from ethanol, yield 60%. Thus the following thiobenzamides were prepared:

- (1) Thiobenzamide¹: pale yellow needles, m.p. 115°.
- (2) *p*-Methylthiobenzamide²: bright yellow plates, m.p. 168°.
- (3) *p*-Chlorothiobenzamide³: yellow plates, m.p. 124°.
- (4) *p*-Methoxythiobenzamide⁴: thick prismatic needles, m.p. 148-49°.

Benzoylacetones were prepared by following the method by Adkins *et al.*⁵ Sodium wire (11.5 g., 0.5 at.) was suspended in ice-cold dry ethyl acetate (200 ml) contained in a 500-ml flask fitted with a reflux condenser. The flask was immersed in an ice bath. Substituted acetophenone (0.25*M*) was added in small lots to the ice-cold ethyl acetate, containing sodium wire, with shaking. Exothermic reaction started and the whole mixture became thick. It was kept overnight. The sodium salts of substituted benzoylacetones were filtered, washed with benzene, and dissolved in water. On acidification with acetic acid, benzoylacetones separated as liquid or solid. These were purified by distillation or crystallisation from ethanol. Yields in general were 70% except for 2, 4-dichlorobenzoylacetone which was obtained in 30% yield. Following benzoylacetones were prepared:

- (1) Benzoylacetone⁶: colorless needles, m.p. 60°.
 - (2) *p*-Methylbenzoylacetone⁶: pale yellow oil, b.p. 280°.
 - (3) *p*-Chlorobenzoylacetone⁶: colorless flakes, m.p. 72-73°.
 - (4) *p*-Methoxybenzoylacetone⁶: colorless plates, m.p. 53-54°.
 - (5) 3,4-Dichlorobenzoylacetone⁷: colorless plates, m.p. 04°.
 - (6) 2, 4-Dichlorobenzoylacetone: colorless long needles, m.p. 49-50°.
- (Found: Cl, 30.51. C₁₀H₈O₂Cl₂ requires Cl, 30.73%).

α-*γ*-Dioxo-*β*-oximino-*α*-phenylbutanes were prepared according to Ceresole⁸. Substituted benzoylacetone (0.1*M*) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (75 ml) and kept stirred in an ice-cold water bath. A solution of sodium nitrite (7 g.) in water (50 ml) was added dropwise during 1 hr. Stirring was continued for another hour. The mixture after keeping for 2 hr. at the room temperature was diluted with water. The precipitated oximino compound was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from ethanol or benzene. Yields in general were 70%. Various oximino compounds are summarised in Table I.

α-*γ*-Dioxo-*β*-oximino-*α*-phenyl-*δ*-bromobutanes.—The preceding oximino compounds (0.025 *M*) were suspended in dry ether and treated with bromine (0.025 *M*, 4.0 g.) in presence of sunlight. The bromo compounds were washed with water to remove hydrobromic acid and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. These crude bromo compounds in ethereal solution were used for condensation with thiobenzamides.

1. Olin and Johnson, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1931, 59, 72.
2. Paterno, *Ber.*, 1975, 8, 441.
3. Kindler, *Annalen*, 1926, 460, 13.
4. Rohlander, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2159.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 3213.
6. Hauser *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 4023.
7. Garg, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 211.
8. *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 816.

TABLE I
 (vide structure I)

No.	R.	R ₁ .	Formula.	Properties.	Found.	Reqd.
1	H	H	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	Colorless prisms from EtOH; m. p. 128°		..
2	H	Me	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	Colorless shining cubes from EtOH; m. p. 165-60°	N: 6.75%	6.83%
3	H	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃ NCl	Colorless plates from EtOH; m. p. 167-68°.	Cl: 15.60	15.74
4	H	OMe	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	Colorless shining crystals from EtOH; m. p. 147-46°	N: 6.30	6.33
5	Cl(2)	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₃ NCl ₂	Colorless shining needles from benzene; m. p. 90-100°	Cl: 27.15	27.30
6	Cl(2)	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₃ NCl ₂	Colorless microneedles from EtOH; m. p. 175°	Cl: 27.18	27.30

Condensation of α,γ-Dioxo-β-azimino-α-phenyl-δ-bromobutanes with Substituted Thiobenzamides.—The crude bromo compounds (0.025 M) were treated with substituted thiobenzamide (0.025 M) in ether. Soon the solution became turbid and the hydrobromides, of the thiazoles started to separate. These solutions were kept overnight. Hydrobromides, thus obtained, were filtered and washed with ether to remove unchanged bromo compounds and thiobenzamides. These were then suspended in water and decomposed by heating with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%) to provide the free bases. The free bases were crystallised from ethanol or ethanol-benzene mixture. The compounds are summarised in Table II.

 TABLE II
 (Vide structure II)

No.	R.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	Formula.	*Properties.	Found.	Reqd.
1	H	H	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	Colorless flat needles; m. p. 180°	N: 9.01%	9.00%
2	H	Me	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	Colorless shining plates; m. p. 169-70°	N: 8.72	8.69
3	H	Cl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	Light yellow microneedles; m. p. 163-64°	Cl: 10.21	10.37
4	H	OMe	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	Colorless granules; m. p. 167-66°	N: 8.26	8.28
5	Cl(2)	Cl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	Colorless needles; m. p. 152-53°	C: 18.71	18.64
6	Cl(3)	Cl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ S	Colorless shining microneedles; m. p. 179-80°	Cl: 18.68	18.64
7	H	H	Me	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	Colorless microneedles; m. p. 182-83°	N: 8.60	8.69
8	H	Me	Me	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	Pale yellow crystals; m. p. 172-73°	N: 8.21	8.28
9	H	Cl	Me	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	Colorless microneedles; m. p. 183-84°	Cl: 9.81	9.96

TABLE II (contd.)

No.	R.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	Formula.	*Properties.	Found.	Reqd.
10	H	OMe	Me	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	Colorless microneedles; m.p. 184-85°	N: 7.89	7.95
11	Cl(2)	Cl	"	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	Colorless microneedles; m.p. 154-55°	Cl: 18.07	18.16
12	Cl(3)	Cl	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	Pale yellow microneedles; mp. 175-76°	Cl: 18.10	18.16
13	H	H	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	Pale yellow needles; m.p. 199-200	Cl: 10.25	10.37
14	H	Me	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	Colorless microneedles; m.p. 175-76°	Cl: 9.99	9.98
15	H	Cl	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	Pale yellow crystals; m.p. 179-80°	Cl: 18.71	18.83
16	H	OMe	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	Colorless microneedles; m.p. 202-203°	Cl: 9.42	9.59
17	Cl(2)	Cl	"	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	Colorless needles; m.p. 173-74°	Cl: 25.75	25.98
18	Cl(3)	Cl	"	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ S	Colorless microneedles; m.p. 202-203°	Cl: 25.79	25.98
19	H	H	OMe	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	Brown crystals; m.p. 196-97°	N: 8.26	8.28
20	H	Me	"	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	Pale brown crystals; m.p. 185-86°	N: 7.84	7.95
21	H	Cl	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	Colorless needles; m.p. 173-74°	Cl: 9.50	9.53
22	H	OMe	"	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	White crystals; m.p. 192-93°	N: 7.52	7.61
23	Cl(2)	Cl	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	Yellow needles; m.p. 177-78°	Cl: 17.33	17.44
24	Cl(3)	Cl	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃ S	Pale yellow needles; m.p. 160-61°	Cl: 17.40	17.44

*All the compounds were crystallized from ethanol except No. 20 and 22, which were crystallized from ethanol-benzene.